

Growth and Mechanical Stability of *Populus* spp. Plantations on Alluvial Soils with Applied Agroforestry Practices in the Region of Vidin

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Abstract

A comparative analysis was conducted on the growth and mechanical stability of *Populus* spp. plantations along the Danube River basin on alluvial soils with a 4x4 m planting scheme and varying ages with applied agroforestry practices. The main soil characteristics have been determined – pH, carbon (C) and nitrogen (N) stock, C/N ratio, and humus content. The growth and productivity of poplar plantations have been assessed through the main dendrometric characteristics – average diameter, average height, stock and mechanical stability coefficient. The plantations show good growth and a low degree of mechanical stability. Of particular economic importance is the cultivation of fast-growing tree species to maximise timber yield in a short period. The initial 4x4 m scheme is suitable for establishment of poplar plantations on alluvial soils, poorly stocked with carbon and nitrogen. Carrying out thinning operations in the poplar plantations around the 5th-6th year after planting would improve the structure, dendrometric characteristics, productivity, and overall strengthening of the stand.

Keywords: *Populus* spp., agroforestry systems, growth, mechanical resilience

Introduction

Agroforestry is a multifunctional, environmentally safe, and modern system of land use. Agroforestry practices are particularly useful for improving the composition of organic matter in the soil – the amount of carbon associated with the resistant fraction increases, while the amount of "aggressive" fulvic acids decreases (Kachova, Ferezliev, 2020).

The establishment of agroforestry systems with the cultivation of tree species along the Danube River shows good results in terms of increasing their productivity and improving soil qualities. Planting agricultural crops, such as corn, melons, and others, among poplars is a good method for increasing their dendrometric characteristics, such as average diameter, average height, and volume. Obtained results provide a reason for agroforestry systems involving *Populus* sp. to be recommended as suitable for establishment along the Danube

River (Kachova, Ferezliev, 2026).

To optimise the productivity of plantations created under specific soil and climatic conditions, it is necessary to understand the development dynamics of these plantations and the changes that occur following the implementation of forestry measures, including when establishing agroforestry systems within them. In the forestry sector of Bulgaria, growing poplar plantations using agroforestry methods has long been a common practice, especially along the Danube River. Young poplar plantations have been co-cultivated with corn, melons, and other agricultural crops, and success has been achieved in improving their growth (Fakirov, 1972; Yakimov et al., 2003; Marinov et al., 2003; Vasev, 2013).

One of the most reliable criteria for assessing the stability of plantations against windthrow, snow breakage, and other mechanical damages to tree stems and crowns, is the mechanical stability coefficient (thinness) (Nykänen et al., 1997; Peltola et al., 1999; Petty, Worrell, 1981; Zhu et al., 2006).

The coefficient of mechanical stability has been tracked by height groups in a study of stands with the edicator Moesian beech (*Fagus moesiaca* (Maly) Czecz.) on the Shumen Plateau (Tsakov et al., 2013). The values of this coefficient are decisive in selecting origins for planting Douglas fir and when conducting thinnings, as the species often suffers from snow and wind breakage (Popov, 2011). This coefficient has been determined in choosing optimal regimes for the establishment and management of Austrian black pine plantations to achieve the maximum total timber utilisation at short rotation and to maintain reliable stability of the stand throughout the entire rotation period (Stankova, 2010). The mechanical stability of plantations from selected *Robinia pseudoacacia* L. clones at ages 5, 7, and 20 has been studied, as well as of plantations on degraded terrains (Dimitrova, 2005; 2019, 2025).

The aim of the present study is to conduct a comparative analysis of the growth and mechanical stability of poplar plantations on alluvial soils with agroforestry practices.

Material and Methods

The objects of study are three poplar plantations established along the Danube River with applied agroforestry practices, following a 4x4 m planting scheme. All sample plots (SP) are located in Natura 2000 and are in the protective riparian zone of the Danube River, where SP1 and SP3 are situated in the territory of the village of Slanotrún, and SP2 in the territory of the town of Vidin.

The soils in the region are alluvial (Alluvial Fluvisol), developed on loess, deep, fresh, sandy, with a groundwater level up to 2 m. Total carbon was determined by the Turin method and total nitrogen by the Kjeldahl method (Donov et al., 1974). Soil samples were taken in three replicates for each sample plot at a depth of 0-20 cm. An average sample was formed for laboratory analyses.

In connection with the study on 9-year-old poplar plantations, sample plots of 2.0 dka in size were established in 2024. Sample plot 2 was established in 2018 with the same size and is used to compare growth and mechanical stability at an older age of over 15 years (table 1).

The heights of the trees in each sample plot were measured with a Vertex IV heightmeter with an accuracy of up to 10 cm. The average height of the stand was calculated using formula (1) of Lorey's (1878):

$$(1) \quad H = \frac{h_1g_1 + h_2g_2 + \dots + h_n g_n}{g_1 + g_2 + \dots + g_n} \text{ (m), where}$$

h – is a height of each tree (1,2, ...,n) (m)

g – is a basal area of each tree (1,2, ...,n) (m²)

Table 1. Description of the sample plots

Sample plot	Poplar clone	Age years	Activities	Altitude m	Exposition
SPSP 1	Agathe F	9	2nd and 3rd year with corn	30	east
SP 2	BL	15	2nd year with corn 3rd year with watermelons	30	northwest
SP 3	Agathe F	9	3rd year with corn	40	east

Complete measuring of all stems in the sample plots has been carried out. The diameter of breast height of each stem ($D_{1.30}$) was determined by measuring two perpendicular diameters at a height of 1.30 m with an accuracy of 1 cm, and the average diameter (D_{av}) of the experimental plot was calculated using the formula (2):

$$(2) \quad D_{av} = \sqrt{1.274 \cdot G_{av}}, \text{ where}$$

D_{av} – average diameter (cm)

$G_{av} = G_{total}/N$ – average basal area (m²)

G_{total} – total basal area (m²)

N – total number of trees

The stem volumes of the poplar trees and the stock of the sample plots in the tables are calculated according to formula (3), derived based on the table of species heights (Krăstănov, 1983).

$$(3) \quad V = (0.32h + 1.74)dbh^2 \times \pi/40000, \text{ where}$$

V – volume of tree (m³)

h – height of tree (m)

dbh – diameter of breast height 1,30 m (cm)

The coefficient of mechanical stability is calculated as ratio ($H/D_{1.30}$) height/diameter of breast height (Schütz, 1999).

The Shapiro-Wilk test has been used to check the normality of the distribution of trees by thickness (Snedecor, Cochran, 1989). For statistical comparison of mean values between two separate groups, the Student's t-test was used (Kalpić et al., 2011).

Results and Discussion

To meet the growing demand for construction timber, selecting suitable large-diameter poplar clones and optimising spacing are essential for increasing plantation productivity. Soil quality is of crucial importance for the development of seedlings. There are studies that confirm the existence of a direct correlation between the height of woody plants and soil conditions (Duhovnikov et al., 1975).

Table 2 presents the main characteristics of the soils in sample plots: pH, C/N ratio, and the stocks of C and N – recalculated in t/ha in 1 cm of soil with an average bulk density taken as 1.5 g/cm³.

Table 2. Characteristics of the soils

Sample plot	pH	Stock of C t/ha	Stock of N t/ha	C/N	Humus %
SP1	6.1	3.46	0.12	27	4.2
SP2	5.8	2.01	0.10	21	2.4
SP3	6.5	2.64	0.11	23	3.3

Soils from the studied sample plots fall within the range of slightly acidic (pH = 5.8 - 6.5). The calculated reserves of carbon and nitrogen indicate that the soils are poorly stocked. The organic matter content is low. Only the soils from SP1 are moderately stocked with organic matter. However, concerning the soil's nitrogen reserves, everywhere it is very low – below 1 t/ha. High summer temperatures and low rainfall during the summer in the area are one of the reasons for the low levels of humus and nitrogen and the active mineralisation of plant residues in the soils along the Danube River (Kirilov et al., 2015). The C/N ratio in the soils, which is an indicator of the rate at which the mineralisation of organic matter occurs, also has low to medium values.

Table 3 presents the summarised dendrometric characteristics of trees in the sample plots of poplar plantations, included in agroforestry systems at the age of 9 (SP1 and SP3) and 15 (SP2) years.

The number of trees per hectare varies from 582 for SP1 to 609 for SP2. The survival rate of individuals in the plantations is over 90%. During the study period, the percentage of fallen individuals varies from 2.6% in SP2 to 6.9% in SP1.

The plantation in SP1 shows better height growth compared to that in SP3, with no difference in diameter growth at the same age. A statistically significant difference was found between the average height of the individuals ($t_{exp}=5.560$, $df=255$, and $Sig=0.001$), and no difference was observed between the average diameter values ($t_{exp}=3.088$, $df=255$, and $Sig=0.080$) in SP1 and SP3. Regarding the dendrobiometrical characteristics, SP2 showed an increase of 19.30 m (250.3%) in average height and 15.4 cm (177.0%) in average diameter

compared to the previous measurement in 2018 (Kachova, Ferezliev, 2026). At the age of 15, the plantation is characterised by relatively good growth and a high stock of 298 m³/ha with an initial growing space of 16 m², without any silvicultural interventions and only about 3% of trees lost.

The comparison of 9-year-old stands by total stock shows that the average annual volume increment is approximately the same, from 7.9 m³/ha for SP1 to 8.4 m³/ha for SP3. The total stock is higher in SP3, which is due to the greater number of trees around the central diameter class 16 (94.6%) and the higher percentage of trees in diameter class 18, which is 5.3% higher than that in SP1.

Table 3. *Dendrometric characteristics of the poplar trees in the sample plots*

Sample plot	Populus clone	Diameter (cm)			Height (m)			Basal area (m ²)		Density No/ha	Volume (m ³ /ha)
		Dmin	Dmax	Dav	Hmin	Hmax	Hav	Gtotal	Gav		
1	Agathe F	12.3	16.8	15.2	11.0	20.0	16.0	2.1774	0.0181	582	67.889
2	BL	17.4	28.7	24.5	16.0	37.0	27.0	6.3410	0.0473	609	298.998
3	Agathe F	11.3	18.7	15.3	9.0	20.0	15.3	2.3694	0.0184	586	71.431

Dav – average diameter, Dmin – minimum and Dmax – maximum tree diameter;
Hav – average height, Hmin – minimum and Hmax – maximum tree height

A distribution of the trees by absolute diameter classes in 2 cm intervals has been carried out. In SP1, poplars are concentrated in four degrees of thickness: 12 (6 trees - 4.7%), 14 (57 trees - 44.5%), 16 (61 trees - 47.7%), and 18 (4 trees - 3.1%). In SP3, the available number of trees (129) is distributed in the following degrees of thickness: 12 (7 trees - 5.4%), 14 (45 trees - 35%), 16 (64 trees - 49.6%), and 18 (13 trees - 10.7%). In 2024, greater differentiation of the trees in SP2 was observed compared to 2018, across 5 degrees as follows: 18 (3 trees - 2.2%), 22 (7 trees - 5.2%), 24 (94 trees - 70.1%), 26 (22 trees - 16.4%) and 28 (8 trees - 6.1%) (Kachova, Ferezliev, 2026). The indicators from the Shapiro-Wilk test (with significance threshold levels $p > 0.05$) show that the distribution of diameters in all sample plots differs statistically significantly from normal ($p < 0.001$) (Table 4).

Table 4. *Percentage distribution of the number of trees from Populus spp. plantations by thickness degrees and normality of the distribution*

Sample plot	Thickness degrees (cm)									Number of trees	Shapiro-Wilk test W	Significance level P
	12	14	16	18	20	22	24	26	28			
	Number of trees (%)											
SP1	4.7	44.5	47.7	3.1						128	0.712	0.000
SP2				2.2		5.2	70.1	16.4	6.1	134	0.704	0.000
SP3	5.4	35	49.6	10.7						129	0.803	0.000

The results confirm the conclusion of a previous study that in poplar plantations, when applying agroforestry practices, regardless of age, higher values of the main dendrobiometrical indicators are recorded in the early stages of growth. Over the years, these

differences diminish (Kachova, Ferezliev, 2020). A probable reason for this is the increased intraspecific competition among the trees, especially regarding the crown, which overrides the initial effect of improved growth conditions (Zhang et al., 2022).

The study shows significant influence of all tending practices on the growth and productivity of poplar plantations. Studies on 12 clones of *Populus x euroamericana* at four densities over a 14-year rotation period indicate that to achieve a diameter of 24 to 35 cm, a growing space of 10 to 32 m² is required, with the optimal period for the first thinning being in the 4th to 5th year (Liu et al., 2025).

In dense plantations, the final timber yield is often lower than the intermediate yields. The first studies on the beginning and intensity of thinning cuts in poplar plantations of *Populus x euroamericana* (Dode) Guinier cv. *regenerata* along the Danube River were conducted by Naydenova and Tsvetkov (1964) and Fakirov (1968). The results indicate that in 5-10-year-old dense plantations, both moderate and intensive thinnings can be carried out depending on the objective. As the age increases and thinning is delayed, more intensive thinning is applied, primarily in medium and small assortments (Fakirov, 1968; Giordano and Avanzo, 1973).

It has been established that plantations of *Populus regenerata* on alluvial-meadow soils along the Danube River with a density of 3x3 m have the highest productivity per hectare, ranging from 425 to 461 m³/ha at the age of 14-16. With the initial planting scheme of 4x4 m, at the same age this productivity is from 304 to 326 m³/ha (Naydenova, Tsvetkov, 1964). Depending on the poplar clone, at a density of 4x4 m, the average volume increment reaches 11-15 m³/ha. Therefore, to increase productivity and produce large timber in a short period, it is recommended to establish less dense plantations. From an economic point of view and for convenience in mechanised soil cultivation, the density should not go below 4x4 m (Fakirov, 1972).

In terms of the number of thinnings, among three thinnings at a 4x4 m density, 4-year-old poplar stands show the best growth in height (8.91 m) and diameter (17.8 cm) (Naydenova, Tsvetkov, 1964). The values of 15.2 cm (SP1) and 15.3 cm (SP3) for the average diameter at 9 years of age of the studied poplar stands indicate that carrying out tending practices would improve their dendrometric characteristics and productivity.

The critical factors regarding site conditions, such as climate conditions, topography, elevation, density, and others, can affect the mechanical resilience of the stands.

Figure 1 presents the values of the mechanical stability coefficient (K_{mst}) for the sample plots of poplars with agroforestry by degrees of thickness (DT). The analysis of the data in the sample plots shows that the stand in sample plot 3 has a better mechanical stability coefficient (1.0), while for the other crops, the average value of this coefficient does not exceed 1.1.

The trees of all thickness grades in SP3 have highest values of the mechanical stability coefficient (≤ 1.0), which determines the best overall resilience of the stand. In SP1, which is of the same age, and in the older plantation (SP2) with a coefficient of 1.0, the trees are from the lower degrees of thickness. In the higher degrees, around which the average diameter is grouped (DT 16 for SP1 and DT 24 for SP2), the highest number of trees is concentrated (64% for SP1 and 69% for SP2) with a resilience coefficient greater than 1.0, which also determines the lower resilience of the stands, regardless of their age.

Fig. 1. Mechanical stability coefficient (K_{mst}) of poplar trees from the sample plots by degrees of thickness

The medium degrees of thickness, represented by the largest number of stems, increase the quantity of large and medium assortments in the plantations (Ferezliev et al., 2018). Regarding the assortment structure for SP2 and the control experimental plot (without agroforestry practice), it was found that the application of an agroforestry system does not significantly affect the type (by categories and classes) of the obtained assortments. Based on the age of the main felling and the average dimensions (height and diameter) of the stand, it is then possible, although approximately, to estimate the dimensions of the harvested assortments in the order of class IV–VI for SP2, encompassing small and medium construction timber (Kachova, Ferezliev, 2026).

The stability of forest stands against windthrow, snow breakage, and other mechanical damages to trees also depends on the tree crown and the density of the stands (Nykänen et al., 1997; Peltola et al., 1999; Petty, Worrell, 1981). The size of the crowns and the arrangement of branches are largely species-specific (Nykänen et al., 1997). The percentage ratio of the crown to the tree height (the so-called crown index) is crucial for the tree and is closely related to its productivity and stability.

Most vulnerable to mechanical damages are trees of smaller diameter classes, regardless of the tree species. Suppressed trees from the lower part of the stand in black locust plantations on degraded lands are characterised by small crowns, increased height growth due to light deficiency, and reduced vitality, which also determines their greater instability (Tsakov, Dimitrova, 2003).

This was also observed in a study of the dynamics of the values of the mechanical stability coefficient by height groups of stands with an edicator Moesian beech (*Fagus moesiaca* (Maly) Czecz.) (Tsakov et al., 2013).

The stems of 7- and 20-year-old black locust plantations from selected *Robinia pseudoacacia* L. clones, grown with an initial growing space of 4.5 m², exhibit a low degree of mechanical stability, confirmed by the H/D_{1.30} ratio. In case a good stock of 200 to 242 m³/ha of wood with impaired stand stability is achieved at lower density, it is recommended to carry out tending measures in the black locust plantations, which would improve dendrobiometric characteristics and the overall strengthening of the stands (Dimitrova, 2019; Dimitrova, 2025).

The data on the influence of density on the stability of stands are highly contradictory (Schütz, 1999; Nykänen et al., 1997; Peltola et al., 1999; Zhu et al., 2006). According to Nykänen et al. (1997), denser stands are less stable because high density promotes the development of thinner stems with asymmetrical and short crowns.

Zhu et al. (2006), in turn, found that with increasing density, the overall size of the main types of mechanical damages (uprooting, breakage, bending, crown disruption) caused by snow and wind in the plantations of various tree species they studied decreases. The authors explain the results by the fact that sparser plantations generally retain less snow, but the amount of snow on individual stems, in turn, is greater, i.e., the exerted pressure is higher.

The damage by a storm was studied on three-year-old plantations of four poplar clones at three densities. It was found that at the closest distance, where crown shaking would be minimised, the trees that were not uprooted had a larger cross-sectional root area in the direction of the wind compared to the uprooted trees. At the greatest distance, where crown shaking would be maximal, the resilient trees had a larger cross-sectional root area not only on the windward side but also on the opposite side. Furthermore, the most susceptible poplar clone had the highest aboveground biomass per unit area of root cross-section (Constance et al., 1996).

When determining the optimal regimes for the sustainable management of poplar plantations with a short rotation, those with good dendrometric characteristics, high productivity, and a coefficient of mechanical stability not exceeding 1.0 are preferred. The initial 4x4 m scheme is suitable for creating poplar plantations along the Danube River. In case a good stock of 298 m³/ha at the age of 15 is achieved with an initial growth space of 16 m², carrying out moderate thinning operations in the poplar plantations around the 5th-6th year after planting would improve the structure, dendrometric characteristics, productivity, and overall strengthening of the stand.

Conclusion

The stands in 9- and 15-year-old plantations of selected *Populus* spp. clones, grown on alluvial soils with agroforestry practices, possess good growth and a low degree of mechanical stability, confirmed by the H/D_{1.30} ratio.

Of particular economic importance is the cultivation of fast-growing tree species to achieve maximum timber yield in a short period. The initial 4x4 m scheme is suitable for creating poplar plantations on alluvial soils, poorly stocked with carbon and nitrogen. Carrying out moderate thinning operations in the poplar plantations around the 5th-6th year after planting would improve the structure, dendrometric characteristics, productivity, and overall strengthening of the stand.

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